

On the egg capsule of *Marginella glabella* (Linné, 1758)

Sobre la cápsula ovígera de *Marginella glabella* (Linné, 1758)

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ABSTRACT

The purse-shaped egg capsule of *Marginella glabella* (Linné, 1758) is described and pictured from a sample collected in Lanzarote, Canary Islands.

Due to the occurrence of the same kind of egg capsule in *M. goodalli* and to the occurrence of plano-convex egg capsules in all other *Marginella* species documented for this character, the shape of the egg capsule is proposed as a further feature characterizing the *M. glabella* species group.

RESUMEN

Se describe y se muestra por primera vez la cápsula ovígera de *Marginella glabella* (Linné, 1758), a partir de una muestra obtenida en Lanzarote, Islas Canarias.

Considerando la ocurrencia del mismo tipo de cápsula ovígera en *M. goodalli* y la ocurrencia de cápsulas plano-convexas en todas las demás especies de *Marginella* para las que existen datos de este carácter, se propone considerar la forma de la cápsula ovígera como un rasgo adicional para caracterizar el grupo de especies en torno a *M. glabella*.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the morphology of the egg capsules of marginelliform gastropods was summarized and discussed by COOVERT (1986), through the presentation of egg capsules attributed to 16 different species.

Twelve of these species belong to the Marginellidae *sensu* Coovert and Coovert, 1995 (2 *Dentimargo* species, 3 *Glabella* species, 1 *Haloginella* species, 2 *Marginella* species, 2 *Prunum* species and 2 *Volvarina* species) and 4 belong to the Cystiscidae *sensu* Coovert and Coovert, 1995 (2 *Granulina* species and 2 *Persicula* species).

On the basis of these data, the Marginellidae species are said to have a plano-convex egg capsule, except for *Marginella goodalli* Sowerby, 1825 from off the Guinean zone, which has a

purse-shaped egg capsule. The Cystiscidae species are said to also have a plano-convex egg capsule, except for *Persicula cornea* (Lamarck, 1822), from the Guinean zone too, which also has a purse-shaped egg capsule.

It is important to note that, in most cases, the specific attribution of the egg capsules recorded by COOVERT (1986) requires further confirmation, the laying of eggs not having been specifically observed and thus the larva being attributed with low certainty to a given species.

KNUDSEN (1950), who is the principal reference used by COOVERT (1986), himself admitted that the method of identification "is not absolutely reliable and possibly some incorrect identifications have been made". However, due to

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the fact that the attribution of purse-shaped egg capsules to *M. goodalli* and to *P. cornea* is proposed by KNUDSEN (1950) with credible arguments, the heterogeneity of egg capsule types within both Marginellidae and Cystiscidae must be provisionally accepted, at least between genera and possibly within some of them.

More recent records of plano-convex egg capsules of Marginellidae species were made by GOFAS AND FERNANDES (1988) concerning *Marginella spinacia* Gofas and Fernandes, 1988 from São Tomé, by FERNANDES AND ROLÁN (1991) concerning *M. eveleighi* Tomlin and Shackleford, 1913 from Principe, and by PENCHASZADEH AND RINCON (1996) concerning *Prunum prunum* (Gmelin, 1791) from Venezuela. The identification of the egg capsules of these two *Marginella* species was made with a high degree of certainty on the basis of the morphologic characters of the larvae, whereas the identification was made with absolute certainty for the *Prunum* species through direct observation of the clutch raised in an aquarium.

The problem raised by the heterogeneity of the egg capsule types within each of the two marginelliform families Marginellidae and Cystiscidae was not tackled by COOVERT (1986), by COOVERT AND COOVERT (1995) or by subsequent authors, despite the fact that any intergrades between the two capsule types under discussion is unknown.

The discovery of a purse-shaped egg capsule attributable to *Marginella glabella* (Linné, 1758), type species of the genus *Marginella* Lamarck, 1799, is presented herein. This new record allows us to reassess the issue of the heterogeneity of egg capsule types in the genus *Marginella*, together with the apparent synapomorphies characterizing the *M. glabella* species group.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The data concerning the clutch of *M. glabella* comes from material and observations communicated by José Hernández.

J. Hernández found a purse-shaped egg-capsule (Figs. 1-2) fixed under a stone

at 3-5 m off Playa Quemada, situated on the southeastern coast of Lanzarote, eastern Canary Islands. The egg capsule contained one larva close to hatching. This larva was removed from the capsule by opening the suture line defined along the cutting edge of the "purse" (Fig. 3) and it was photographed out of the capsule (Fig. 4). The shell of this larva was compared with the protoconch of live collected adult specimens of *M. glabella* (Fig. 5) sampled in the vicinity by Francisco Sicilia and Javier Lopez-Vicente.

The terms "plano-convex" and "purse-shaped" egg capsule are used by preference, respectively, to the terms "lenticular or lens-shaped capsule" and "lenticular capsule with a flat base" used by COOVERT (1986). This preference is due to the inadequately descriptive meaning of "lenticular" applied to the cases considered, and to the ambiguity introduced by the use of the same word for defining two different types of capsule morphology. As a matter of fact, the two types of egg capsules examined differ not only in the way they are attached to the substrate (via a basal membrane extending beyond the capsule walls in the case of the plano-convex type, versus via a more or less produced stalk in the case of the purse-shaped type), but also in the way the capsules are torn open at the hatching stage [along a suture line surrounding the hemispherical upper side of the capsule quite close to the base in the plano-convex type (see in COOVERT, 1986), versus escape from an "exit hole" at the top of the capsule (see in KNUDSEN, 1950: 121) or along the cutting edge of the lateral borders (this work)].

RESULTS

The attribution of the purse-shaped egg capsule found off Playa Quemada to the species *M. glabella* is based on the morphology of the larval shell removed from the capsule.

The outline of this capsule looks quite like that of a chicken egg horizontally oriented and put on a ventrally fixed short stem. The capsule is laterally compressed, smooth, hyalinous light honey-amber. The

Figures 1-5. *Marginella glabella*, Playa Quemada, Lanzarote. 1,2: egg capsule, view from both sides, width= 7 mm; 3: hatching of the larva; 4: larval shell with animal retracted; 5: adult shell, length= 26 mm.

Figuras 1-5. Marginella glabella, Playa Quemada, Lanzarote. 1-2: cápsula ovígera, vistas desde ambos lados, ancho= 7 mm; 3: eclosión de la larva; 4: concha larvaria con el animal retraído; 5: concha adulta, longitud= 26 mm.

total height of this capsule is 5 mm, the height of the "purse" is 4 mm, its width is 7 mm, and the stalk length is 1 mm. The shell of the larva perfectly matches by its shape, its consistency, its colour and its size (1,3 mm at the base line of its upper quarter, 2 mm at its wider diameter) the protoconch (width: 1,3 mm) of the *M. glabella* adult specimens found in the vicinity (compare Figures 4 and 5). No other gastropod species from this geographical area show a similar protoconch.

DISCUSSION

M. glabella is shown to have an egg capsule of the purse-shaped type, like the congeneric species *M. goodalli*. The egg capsule described by KNUDSEN (1950) for *M. goodalli* is quite different from that of *M. glabella*, due to its taller, more produced, subcylindrical outline, but both species can be said to have the same type of egg capsule, deeply different from the plano-convex egg capsules

of the supposedly congeneric *M. cleryi*, *M. spinacia* and *M. eveleighi*, and of the closely related *Glabella adansonii* (Kiener, 1834), *Dentimargo aureocincta* (Stearns, 1872) and *D. cairoma* (Brookes, 1924).

Other characters shared by *M. glabella* and *M. goodalli* are rather inflated non-sculptured orange to reddish shells with white marks or spots, and orange animals with white spots or dots. On the basis of personal observations of live specimens in Senegal, the species proposed to belong to the *M. glabella* species group together with *M. glabella* and *M. goodalli* are *M. aurantia* (Lamarck, 1822), *M. desjardini* (Marche-Marchad, 1957), *M. sebastiani* (Marche-Marchad and Rosso, 1979) and *M. lamarcki* (Boyer, 2004). The specific validity of other taxa commonly linked to this group (like *M. irrorata* Menke, 1828 and *M. pseudosebastiani* Mattavelli, 2001) remains dubious and requires further investigation.

The possession of the same type of egg capsule is considered here as a further synapomorphy defining the *M. glabella* species group as very distinct from the other *Marginella*, *Glabella* and *Dentimargo* species groups.

A noticeable plasticity is often observed at the individual level in egg capsules of marine gastropods, and a noticeable disparity in the details of the capsule morphology is often observed

between species belonging to the same genus. For instance, ROLÁN AND RAYBAUDI MASSILIA (1995) showed the high variability of the egg capsules in *Conus mediterraneus* and MORENO AND TEMPLADO (1995) demonstrated that the sibling species *Nassarius cuvieri* and *N. unifasciatus* from the Lusitanian Province have very distinct egg capsules despite the similarity of their shell characters. However the type of egg capsule seems to be homogeneous in monophyletic groups: purse-shaped type in *C. mediterraneus* and cushion-shaped type in the *N. cuvieri*/*N. unifasciatus* series.

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